

Gender Based Violence Among Civil Servants in Bauchi State and Its Implications on Marriage and Work

Gbatse, Victoria H. & Kembe, Elizabeth M.

Abstract

This study investigated Gender-Based Violence (GBV) among civil servants and its implication on marriage and work in Bauchi State. The study was guided by three objectives and one hypothesis. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. Civil servants and married people in nine selected Local Government Areas of Bauchi State formed the population and this was made of eight thousand five hundred and fifty-five state civil servants. The sample size of three hundred and seventy-four (374) was drawn from the nine Local Government Areas. The study used proportionate random sampling technique to select the sample using Taro Yamane Formula. The instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire entitled "Gender-Based Questionnaire" (GBQ). Descriptive statistics was used to analyse the data collected using simple percentage and mean to answer the research objectives, while Chi-square was used to test the hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study identified failure on the part of men to provide all the family needs, male dominance such as varied duties and jobs assigned to men and women by the society as some of the gender roles that foster gender-based violence in Bauchi State. The study found physical, emotional, and sexual violence; human trafficking, prostitution and homosexuality as types of gender-based violence that are experienced by both male and female in Bauchi State. The findings of the study further revealed significant relationship between work, level of education and GBV among working class families ($\chi^2 = 107.947^n$ ($df = 3$) $P = 0.000 < 0.05$ in Bauchi State. The study concluded that GBV has an influence on marriage and work among working class families. Based on this conclusion, the study recommended, involvement of NGO's and mass media in creating awareness on gender -based violence, attitudinal change by the people and promulgation of policies and laws on family welfare to curb gender-based violence.

Key Words: *Gender-Based Violence, Psychological Violence, Work, honour killing, domestic violence,*

Introduction

Gender-based violence (GBV) is viewed as a global phenomenon (Al Usta, Dandashi & Anani, 2012), transcending socio-economic status, ethnicity, religion and language groups. According to Sida (2015), gender-based violence is viewed as any harm or suffering that is perpetrated against a woman or girl, man or boy that has a negative impact on the physical, sexual or psychological health, development or identity of the person.

Gender-based violence includes physical, sexual and psychological violence such as domestic violence, sexual abuse, including rape and sexual abuse of children by family members; sexual slavery, traditional practices harmful to women, such as honour killings, burning or use of acid, female genital mutilation, dowry-related violence, violence in armed conflicts, emotional abuse such as coercion and abusive language, trafficking of women and girls, prostitution, sexual

harassment, and intimidation at work (GBVIMS, 2010; Al Usta, Dandashi & Anani, 2012; FAO, 2018).

Gender-based violence is not restricted to violence against women; it generally constitutes a violation of human rights and forms of discrimination against men and women. GBV has been broadly classified as Violence Against Women (VAW) and Violence Against Men (VAM). Animasaun and Animasaun (2013) see VAM (men-based violence) in two folds: Intended Violence against Men (IVAM) and Unintended Violence against Men (UVAM). The former deals with those actions which fall within the motives behind female-male gender-based violence while the latter, is classified as acts or practices ignorantly done based on domestic and patriarchal dictates which can affect the man.

According to WHO (2019), gender refers to the socially constructed characteristics of women and men such as norms, roles, and relationships between groups of women and men. It varies from society to society. The term "sex" and gender" are used synonymously, for instance, sex differences in childbearing and in physical strength are used as criteria for determining division of labour and the distribution of resources in many societies. Differences in human functions such as conception and childbearing, breast feeding, insemination and fertilization are biologically determined by sex roles (Regitz-Zagrosek, 2012).

Gender-based violence in the workplace is a broad concept that is concerned with behaviour that occurs both on and off the workplace. This includes all behaviour that interferes with worker's capability to be safe to perform their assigned duties at workplace. These kinds of conducts range from harassment or repeated telephone calls or faxes at work to unarmed and armed "show-ups" and homicide (Ajala, 2008). Bauchi state is predominantly hinged on very strong and religious values and these values influence both family and work life, It is on this note that it becomes necessary to carry this study to ascertain if gender-based

violence has an influence on civil servants work and marriage in Bauchi State.

Statement of the Problem

Gender-based violence occurs in homes, schools, among family members and people in various relationships, (WHO 2012). Civil servants who experience marital conflicts and gender -based violence are likely to produce children who are vulnerable to problems of personality adjustment or abnormalities; such children are considered vulnerable to a range of short- and long-term physical, mental, and sexual consequences (Aihie, 2009). Gender-based violence is most likely to lead to injuries that are severe thereby causing the victim to take time off from work, absenteeism, or less stable workforce and low labour productivity. It is likely to affect the stability of marriages and families. It is quite observable to see gender-based violence in Bauchi state especially affecting women and men in various ways. Empirical evidence reveals that six in ten women in the Northeast part of Nigeria have experienced some form of battering, neglect and financial emasculation (Nigeria Humanitarian Response Plan, 2018). Many families have been devastated because of gender-based violence. Therefore, this study sought out to find out roles that foster gender-based violence, the types of gender-based violence that influence both male and female on work productivity.

Objective of the Study

The general objective of this study is to investigate gender-based violence among civil servants and its implications on marriage and work in Bauchi state. The specific objectives are:

1. Identify gender roles that foster gender-based violence in Bauchi State.
2. Identify the various types of gender-based violence among working class families in Bauchi State.
3. Determine whether work type and education are determinants for gender-based violence among working class families in Bauchi state.

Research Hypothesis

The study was guided by the following null hypothesis. There is no significant relationship between work, level of education and prevalence of Gender-based violence among working class families in Bauchi State.

Methodology

Research Design

This study made use of a descriptive survey design. The research adopted the research survey design because it can gather information from a wide range of people and the result is generalisable to other regions and aspects of gender-based violence.

Population

The population of the study comprised working-class men and women who work with the state civil service from selected nine Local Government Areas in the three Senatorial Districts of Bauchi state. The total population of civil servants in the selected Local Government Areas was made up of eight thousand five hundred and fifty-seven (8, 557) civil servants (Local Government Civil Service Commission, 2019). The area for this study is Bauchi State and primarily it covers nine (9) Local Government Areas of Bauchi State namely; Katagum, Gamawa, Shira, Zaki, Jamaare, Itas-Gadau, Danbam, Giade and Misau Local Government Areas.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

The study employed proportionate random sampling technique to draw samples from the selected nine Local Government Areas of Bauchi State. A sample of 380 respondents was drawn using Taro Yamane Formula:

$$N = \frac{N}{1 + N e^2}$$

n stands for sample size required while N stands for number of people in the population (8,557) and, e represents allowable error (5% or 0.05).

Method of Data Collection

The instrument used for this study was a questionnaire titled "Gender-Based Questionnaire" (GBQ). The instrument was composed of a four-point scale of preference thus: Strongly Agreed (SA) = 4, Agreed (A) = 3, Disagreed (D) = 2, and Strongly Disagreed (SD) = 1.

To determine the validity of the research instrument, three (3) copies of the instrument were given to three (3) experts in the Department of Home Science and Management, Joseph Sarwuan Tarka University, Makurdi for face and content validity. Completed questionnaire were collected on the spot and upon assessment, three hundred and seventy-four (374) copies were correctly completed.

Data Analysis Techniques

Descriptive statistics was used to analyse the data collected using simple percentage and mean. Any mean of 2.50 and above were acceptable while below 2.50 were not acceptable. Chi-square was employed to test the hypothesis.

Results

Table (1) revealed responses of participants on the gender roles that foster gender-based violence in Bauchi State. Fifteen items were presented, 9 of these items all agree on the socialization roles assigned to men and women help to promote gender-based violence as all items score above 2.50.

Table1: Mean Responses on the Gender Roles that Foster Gender-Based Violence in Bauchi State.

S/NO	ITEMS	SA 4	A 3	D 2	SD 1	\bar{X}	DECISION
1.	Failure on the part of men to provide all the family needs lead to Gender-Based Violence.	32.6	52.7	12.8	1.9	3.16	Agree
2.	Socialization practices with dominance and submissive roles for boys and girls contributes to GBV	21.1	49.7	26.5	2.7	2.89	Agree
3.	The duties and jobs assigned to men and women by the society help to promote gender-based violence.	13.9	38.0	36.6	11.5	2.54	Agree
4.	Men who help their wives with domestic chores are seen as weak, incompetent, and Feminine	21.7	28.1	26.2	24.1	2.47	Disagree
5.	Men who allow their wives to work for paid work outside the home suffer gender-based violence	11.8	23.3	43.9	21.1	2.26	Disagree
6.	Different Gender roles for boys and girls positively help them to become better people.	31.0	51.6	15.8	1.6	3.12	Agree
7.	Dual work roles and work pressure is a form of gender-based abuse.	7.8	28.6	53.5	10.2	2.34	Disagree
8.	Housework is another form of domestic abuse	4.8	8.3	44.7	42.2	1.76	Disagree
9.	There is no relationship between gender roles and gender-based violence	10.2	31.0	42.2	16.6	2.35	Disagree
10.	There is a relationship between roles and different forms of gender-based abuse.	13.9	53.6	23.6	8.8	2.73	Agree
11.	Housework is only meant for women and children in the family.	8.6	16.6	35.8	39.0	1.95	Disagree
12.	Boys do not like house chores.	21.7	44.4	25.9	8.0	2.80	Agree
13.	Girls carry out more responsibility at home than boys.	42.8	43.6	10.7	2.9	3.26	Agree
14.	Boys who are not given responsibility at home grow up to be lazy.	37.2	44.4	13.9	4.5	3.14	Agree
15.	Mutual role and responsibilities sharing between boys and girls is not commonly acceptable.	17.1	42.2	26.5	14.2	2.62	Agree

Table (2) revealed responses of participants on the type of gender-based violence that is common to males and females in Bauchi State. Fifteen items were presented, eleven

(11) of these items all agree had mean values of 2.50 and above while 3 of the items disagreed had with values below the cut-off point of 2.50.

Table2: Mean responses on the type of gender-based violence that is common to Males and Females in Bauchi State

S/NO	ITEMS	SA 4	A 3	D 2	SD 1	\bar{X}	DECISION
1.	Physical aggression like battery is a common form of violence among couples.	31.0	48.1	15.0	5.9	3.04	Agree
2.	Physical, emotional and sexual violence such as Rape and sexual harassment are common forms of gender-based violence.	38.5	48.4	10.2	2.9	3.22	Agree
3.	Male and female both experience sexual harassment	21.9	47.3	23.8	7.0	2.84	Agree
4.	Human trafficking is not a type of Gender-Based Violence in Bauchi State.	4.8	21.4	43.6	30.2	2.01	Disagree
5.	Forced prostitution and homosexuality are types of Gender-based violence.	27.0	37.4	25.4	10.2	2.82	Agree
6.	Verbal abuse is a common form of Gender-based violence against men.	23.8	55.1	19.3	1.9	3.01	Agree
7.	Children are mostly likely to be abused.	40.9	46.0	9.6	3.5	3.24	Agree
8.	Women are battered at home more	29.1	44.1	18.2	8.6	2.94	Agree
9.	Incest is common among working class family.	9.9	39.6	36.6	13.9	2.45	Disagree
10.	Female genital mutilation is not a gender-based violence.	6.1	23.5	37.7	32.6	2.03	Disagree
11.	Men suffer gender-based violence as much as women.	8.8	32.6	42.0	16.6	2.34	Disagree
12.	There are also men prostitutes.	22.7	44.7	25.7	7.0	2.83	Agree
13.	Early marriage and forced marriage are types of gender-based violence.	32.1	48.9	11.8	7.2	3.06	Agree
14.	Refusal of women/wives by their spouse from engaging in a trade and economic activities is a form of abuse.	19.5	40.6	28.9	11.0	2.69	Agree

Table (3) revealed responses on work and level of education as determinants for gender-based violence among working class families in Bauchi State. Fourteen (14) items were presented, nine (9) of these items all agree that level of education can influence gender-based violence (2.69), work can influence gender-based violence (2.86), poverty makes women and girls to experience gender-based violence (3.15), women and girls who have less education, experience gender-based

violence than those who have high educational qualification and experience (3.03), women are most likely to suffer sexual abuse in the place of work (3.04), work affects gender-based violence (2.83), long work hours and high income contribute to gender-based violence (2.88) and poor remuneration contributes to gender-based violence (2.61) while five (5) items were disagreed: with value below the cut-off point of 2.50.

Table3: Mean Responses of Participants on the Type of Work and Education Determinants for Gender-Based Violence among Working Class Families in Bauchi State.

S/NO	ITEMS	SA 4	A 3	D 2	SD 1	N	\bar{X}	DECISI
1.	The level of education one acquires can influence gender-based violence.	16.6	45.0	29.5	8.8	374	2.69	Agree
2.	Type of work one does can influence gender-based violence.	20.1	50.5	25.1	4.3	374	2.86	Agree
3.	Poverty makes women and girls to experience gender-based violence.	34.8	49.2	12.0	4.0	374	3.15	Agree
4.	Women are given equal treatment with men in religion and workplaces.	12.6	22.5	39.3	25.7	374	2.22	Disagree
5.	Denial of women access to work does not contribute to high rate of gender-based violence among educated family.	7.0	45.2	36.4	11.5	374	2.48	Disagree
6.	Women and girls who have low educational attainment experience gender-based violence than those who have high educational qualification and experience.	31.3	47.1	15.5	6.1	374	3.03	Agree
7.	Unemployment does not make women and girls to experience gender-based violence.	3.2	22.5	56.1	18.2	374	2.11	Disagree
8.	Women are most likely to suffer sexual abuse in the place of work	24.6	57.8	15.0	2.7	374	3.04	Agree
9.	Culture does not encourage equal treatment in workplaces.	16.8	44.7	33.2	5.3	374	2.73	Agree
10.	Women who earn more income in the family lead to gender-based violence	14.7	34.8	32.2	17.4	374	2.47	Disagree
11.	Type of work affects gender-based violence.	8.8	69.5	17.4	4.3	374	2.83	Agree
13.	Long work hours and high income contribute to gender-based violence.	19.8	48.9	22.2	8.8	374	2.88	Agree
14.	Poor remuneration contributes to gender-based violence.	9.4	48.9	35.3	6.4	374	2.61	Agree

Test of Hypothesis

The null hypothesis states: There is no significant relationship between work, level of education and prevalence of GBV among working class families in Bauchi State.

Table (4) revealed that $(X^{2cal}) = 107.947^a$ (df =3) $P= 0.000 < 0.05$. The hypothesis that states there is no significant relationship between work, level of education and prevalence of

gender-based violence among working class families in Bauchi State is hereby rejected. This implies that there is significant relationship between work, level of education and prevalence of gender-based violence among working class families in Bauchi State.

Table 4: Chi-Square Relationship between Work Type, Educational Attainment and Prevalence of Gender-Based Violence among Working Class Families in Bauchi State

Opinion	Observed N	Expected N	Residual	Level of sig.	Df	X ² _{cal}	P-value	Decision Sig.
SD	36	93.5	-57.5	0.05	3	107.947 ^a	.000	Sig.
D	106	93.5	12.5					
A	169	93.5	75.5					
SA	63	93.5	-30.5					

a. 0 cells (0.0%) have expected frequencies less than 5. The minimum expected cell frequency is 93.5.

Discussions

Results from table 1 revealed responses of participants on the gender roles that foster gender-based violence in Bauchi State. Fifteen items were presented, 9 of these items all agree on the roles that foster gender-based violence to include but not limited to the following: failure on the part of men to provide all the family needs lead to gender-based Violence (3.16), Nigerian socialization practices with dominance and submissive roles for boys and girls contributes to GBV (2.89), the duties and jobs assigned to men and women by the society help to promote gender-based violence (2.54), different Gender roles for boys and girls positively help them to become better people (3.12), girls carry out more responsibility at home than boys (3.26), and boys who are not given responsibility at home grow up to be lazy (3.14). Barker (2011) and Greene (2011) revealed that gender norms such as social expectations of appropriate roles, behaviours of both men and boys, women and girls, transmission of norms by institutions and cultural practices have direct influence on gender-based violence and other health-related behaviours.

Results from table 2 present responses of participants on the type of gender-based violence that is common to males and females in Bauchi State. Physical aggression (3.04), physical, emotional and sexual abuse (3.22), male and female both experience sexual harassment (2.84), forced prostitution and homosexuality (2.82), verbal abuse is a common form of Gender-based violence against men (3.01), early marriage and forced marriage (3.06) and refusal of women and wives by their spouses from engaging in a trade and economic activities (2.62) are

all types of gender-based violence affecting both marriages and the workplace.

The findings of the study agree with (GBVIMS, 2010; Al Usta, Dandashi and Anani, 2012; FAO, 2018) who variously report on gender-based violence experienced by both men and women to include, rape, sexual slavery, trafficking, forced pregnancy, sexual harassment, sexual exploitation and abuse (forced prostitution), sexual slavery and transactional sex.

Results from table 3 revealed responses of participants on the work and level of education as determinants for gender-based violence among working class families in Bauchi State. Fourteen items were presented, nine (9) of these items all agree that the level of education one acquires can influence gender-based violence (2.69), work can influence gender-based violence (2.86), women are most likely to suffer sexual abuse in the place of work (3.04). The findings are in line with Abramsky, Watts, Garcia-Moreno, Devries, Kiss, Ellsberg, Jansen & Heise (2011) who revealed that level of education is the most consistent factor associated with both perpetrating and experiencing gender-based violence.

The results from the hypothesis indicate significant relationship between work, level of education and prevalence of gender-based violence among working class families in Bauchi State ($\chi^2 = 107.947^a$ (df = 3) P = 0.000 < 0.05. According to Haaga, Aja & Chukwuemeka (2015), education is one of the ways of tackling gender-based violence. Ybarra, Bull, Kiwanuka, Bangsberg & Korchmaros (2012) and Mekuria, Nigussie & Abera (2015) reports that a father who had completed primary or lower secondary

school is less likely to be associated with sexual violence while Bekele, Kaso, Gebremariam & Deressa (2015) found out that women who had less education such as primary school level decreased the prevalence of sexual violence compared with illiterate women in the society. The study affirms that gender - based violence is common and affects work and families.

Conclusion and Recommendations

From the findings in the study, it can be concluded that gender-based violence influences marriage and work especially among working class families. The study establishes that there is a relationship between work and level of education and gender-based violence among working class families. This is because education positions to be responsible in the society, as well as acquire the knowledge to avoid gender-based violence. Based on the findings, the following recommendations are made:

1. Non-Governmental Organizations and the mass media (Radio, television, billboards advertisements) should continually create awareness on the impact of gender-based violence on work and marriage stability. Traditional rulers, heads of faith-based institutions like the heads of Muslims and Christian groups should use their various platforms to preach against this menace.
2. Attitudinal change is required by people on some of the socialization practices that foster gender-based violence. People should be willing to imbibe the positive attitude and practice toward the opposite gender.
3. Government of Bauchi state should use policies and laws that will promote family welfare and create the enabling environment for both male and female gender to strive in the workplace.

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